

Best-fitting models

We present the FASTWIND best-fitting model to the observed spectra for one star of the Car OB1 O-type population analyzed in the article *Gaia-ESO Survey: massive stars in the Carina Nebula. II. The spectroscopic analysis of the O-star population* (Berlanas et al. 2025, A&A, in press). The observed spectra (in black) is overplotted to the best-fitting model (in red) resulting from the `iacob-gbat` analysis. Each star is labeled with its name and the model. He I, He II and H lines are indicated with solid, dashed and dotted short vertical lines, respectively.

